

**ADAPTABILITY OF TRADITIONS AND CUSTOM TO MODERN
CONDITIONS AND NEW FORMS OF ART ON THE EXAMPLE OF THE
SURKHANDARYA REGION.**

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Annotation: This report considers the main problem of the gradual loss of interest in folklore art and global urbanisation, which has the main impact on this process. In the presentation of the report, attention is paid to the methods of solving this issue, taking into account the interests of the new generation and new forms of art. Also in the process of analysis, the possibility of developing folklore art is considered, through modernisation taking into account the interests of the new time.

Keywords: Traditions, customs, folklore art, dance folklore art, Surkhandarya region.

In the era of urbanization, traditions and customs are in danger of extinction, which is facilitated by the mixing of cultures and the mutual penetration of assimilation peoples into the established way of life. In order to preserve traditions in modern society, it is necessary to adapt and popularize them, based on the experience of the older generation. The emergence of traditions is due to spiritual knowledge of the environment.

The relevance of the chosen topic is due to the high importance of preserving and transferring cultural values to the new generation, as the identity of the people flows from the traditions

The consideration of the Surkhandarya region, which is little studied, but at the same time has important strategic and historical significance, is due to a clear example for further study and the possibility of adaptation in modern society, folklore art, which has not lost its identity.

The study of Surkhandarya's dance folklore will contribute to the disclosure of its enduring aesthetic value and significant role in the modern artistic culture of Uzbekistan. On the territory of Surkhandarya, folklore art remained in its original form and did not lose its originality, formed in the process of layering historical time layers. To preserve traditional culture, it is necessary to develop and supplement them with new information of the present time, only in this case it is possible to develop the cultural base of the people. An important task of professional education and researchers is to popularize and attract the future generation to folk art.

When studying the problems of the issue raised, the main material was made by the studies of historians, theorists and practitioners of dance art, in particular, candidates of art history L.A.Avdeeva, G.R.Khamrayeva, M.V.Israilov, R.Karimova gives an opportunity to get the most general idea of the ways of development of the Uzbek national dance art from ancient times to the present day. Features of the formation and historical development of the Uzbek people, their way of life, rites, traditions, customs, material and intangible culture, including dance culture, are vividly highlighted and important in the study, the works of the famous culturologist, academician I.D. Dzhabbarov.

L.Avdeeva's works provide extensive information about the culture and way of life of the Uzbek people. In particular, various dance schools, subjects and attributes used in ritual dances, preserved in some areas of Uzbekistan to this day, are described in detail.

The main purpose of studying this issue is to determine possible methods of preservation, popularization and modernization of folklore art and traditions in modern society.

Currently, with the introduction of new technologies and public interest in more progressive activities, there is an active growth in other sectors of life and science. But it should be understood that the erased boundaries between

nationalities, culture and art can lead to the loss of identity, national color and spirituality of society.

The study of the Surkhondarya region clearly shows that traditions and customs continue to be preserved on the territory of Uzbekistan, as a result of the active contribution of amateur folklore groups, which, adhering to the personal interest and experience of the previous generation, continue to preserve and transfer from generation to generation the experience accumulated over the centuries. Professional teams, in turn, with respect and awe preserving the specifics, adding stage and entertainment, bring modernised productions to large stages, thereby attracting interest in traditional art among the younger generation.

In conclusion, it is worth noting that in modern conditions, the creative activity of folklore and ethnographic ensembles "Baysun", "Barchina", "Shamsukamar", "Zevar", "Okhvokh" and children's ensembles "Kuralay" and "Chashma", "Sashma" is of great importance in preserving the folklore traditions of Surkhondarya. In the work of ensembles, folk dance in all its glory came to the stage. Laureate of international festivals The "Baysun" ensemble presented the beauty of Uzbek folk dance in many countries of the world. The programs of the ensembles include both individual musical and dance compositions and the dramatization of folk rites. The main task of the artistic life of ensembles is the revival and preservation of national dance traditions.

Currently, the process of formation of stage forms of Surkhondarya dance folklore is noticeable. This phenomenon acquires a bright character in the ballet master's work of Sh. Kurbanova in her author's productions for the ensemble "Shamsukamar". The folk dance in the program of the ensemble is represented by poetic motifs of girlish dances and splashing Bacchic joy of youth dances. In the stage interpretation of Sh. Kurbanova's folklore dance broke out with bright colors.

The musical activity of schools and houses of culture is important in preserving customs and traditions in modern society. In each, even the most remote settlement

of Surkhandarya, the population actively participates in the activities of local art events.

-It is necessary to launch new programs both at the regional and international level to popularise culture

- It is necessary to actively involve means of social communication and organise large scientific expeditions in order to study in detail the origins of culture.

-It is to involve artists of all kinds of arts to study and propose methods of development and stage adaptation, as professional forms of art, folklore folk art.

Each new generation affirms its own values. Values can be revived, acquire a new sound in modern forms. Nevertheless, there are also eternal values. Ethnocultural values are a huge intellectual wealth and an inexhaustible reserve of reproduction of universal values, cultural and moral traditions of peoples, the process of national creation.

List of references:

Labours of the Presidents of the Republic of Uzbekistan

Karimov I.A. High spirituality is an invincible force. - T.: Uzbekistan, 2008.

Sh.M. Mirziyoyev Buyuk kelazhagimizni mard va olizhanob halkimiz bilan birga kuramiz. T.: "Ozbekiston", 2017.

Speech of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Shavkat Mirziyoyev at the solemn ceremony dedicated to the opening of the International Festival of Bakhshi Art. The "Pravda of the East" newspaper. № 68 (29031). 04/07/2019.

Basic literature:

Abdullaev R. Rite and music in the context of the culture of Uzbekistan and Central Asia. T., 2006.

Avdeeva L.A. From the history of Uzbek national choreography. - T.: 2001.

Bayburin A.K. Ritual in traditional culture. - St. Petersburg, 1993

Gumilev L.N. Ethnogenesis and the Earth's biosphere. - M., 1992.

Khakimov A. Art of Uzbekistan: history and modernity. T., 2010.

Festivals. Just like many years ago. Uzbekistan Today. 5.04.2015.

Rtveladze E. Civilisations, states, cultures of Central Asia. T., 2005.

Kurbanova Sh. Khursandov Kh. Surkhan dance school. T., 2010.

Nasibulina L. History of Uzbek choreographic art. T., 2019.

Internet sites:

[Ytt//www.ziyonet.uz](http://www.ziyonet.uz)

[Htt//www.kitobxon.uz](http://www.kitobxon.uz)

[Htt//www.kultura.uz](http://www.kultura.uz)

[Htt//www.bibliofond.ru](http://www.bibliofond.ru)

[Www.bibliotekar.ru](http://www.bibliotekar.ru)

[Tochka-na-karte.ru](http://tochka-na-karte.ru)

Alpamish media (YouTube)